

DEVELOPMENT OF A DASHBOARD FOR NURSING-SENSITIVE INDICATORS

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Background

- Care improvement /cost containment high healthcare priorities
- Nursing represents the largest healthcare discipline in the Los Angeles County Department of Health Services (LACDHS)
- Improving the quality of nursing care is instrumental in achieving overall quality improvement and cost effectiveness
- Nursing-Sensitive Indicators (NSIs) provide measures for assessing the quality and impact of nursing care delivery
- Monitoring and trending NSIs is essential to ongoing nursing care improvement and enhancement of patient outcomes
- Data dashboards provide an effective tool for NSI monitoring and visual display of nursing care quality

Problem Statement

At LACDHS:

- Assessing NSI performance occurs only at facility level
- Lack of consistency in nursing data collection, aggregation, analysis, and reporting at corporate level
- Fragmented quality improvement processes
- No opportunities to monitor systemwide performance.

Purpose Statement

- Develop, evaluate, and implement a NSI dashboard for LACDHS Office of Nursing Affairs (ONA).
- Incorporate dashboard as visual management tool for system-wide nursing quality improvement

Methods

- Design: Evidence-based practice quality improvement project
- Setting: Los Angeles County Health Services (LACDHS) Office of Nursing Affairs (ONA)
- Measures: Perceived usefulness of dashboard by LACDHS Nursing Executive Team
- Evaluation: Dashboard design, ease of use, appropriateness of data levels
- Perceived usefulness for ongoing NSI monitoring

Theoretical Framework

Model for Improvement

A. Three Questions

- What are we trying to accomplish?**
Creating a method to allow the LACDHS to monitor system-wide performance of nursing care
- How will we know that a change is an improvement?**
Satisfaction level of stakeholders and perceptions of usefulness of a designed NSI Dashboard
- What changes can we make that will result in improvement?**
 - Selection of agreed upon NSIs for evaluation throughout LACDHS
 - Create a dashboard of NSIs
 - Display results to identify quality improvement activities

B. Plan, Do, Study, Act Cycle

The API Model for Improvement (Health Catalyst, 2018)

Dashboard Prototype

		4th Quarter 2018	1st Quarter 2019	2nd Quarter 2019	3rd Quarter 2019
HAPI	% of Pt. with Hospital Acq. Press. Injuries All Categories	Hospital A: 4.07	Hospital B: 0.61	Hospital C: 0.00	Hospital D: 3.92
		Hospital A: 1.41	Hospital B: 2.94	Hospital C: 0.00	Hospital D: 2.04
		Hospital A: 1.21	Hospital B: 3.85	Hospital C: 1.65	Hospital D: 4.26
		Hospital A: 0.92	Hospital B: 1.01	Hospital C: 0.87	Hospital D: 2.63
Falls	Falls per 1000 Pt Days	Hospital A: 2.31	Hospital B: 1.20	Hospital C: 1.20	Hospital D: 1.94
		Hospital A: 107	Hospital B: 2.6	Hospital C: 2.2	Hospital D: 13
		Hospital A: 102	Hospital B: 1.7	Hospital C: 3.1	Hospital D: 14
		Hospital A: 87	Hospital B: 3.2	Hospital C: 1.9	Hospital D: 7
Falls	All Injury Falls per 1000 Patient Days	Hospital A: 0.25	Hospital B: 0.16	Hospital C: 0.00	Hospital D: 0.00
		Hospital A: 24	Hospital B: 1	Hospital C: 0	Hospital D: 0
		Hospital A: 13	Hospital B: 3	Hospital C: 1	Hospital D: 1
		Hospital A: 11	Hospital B: 0	Hospital C: 2	Hospital D: 2

Results

- Satisfaction with the Proposed Dashboard**
- Overall satisfaction with design, value, and presentation of results
- Satisfaction with the Dashboard Meeting Needs**
- This evaluation included responses to the five questions.

The Nursing Executive Team satisfaction with:

- Content alignment with needs and desires of stakeholders
- Design supports needs of facilities and ongoing reporting to accrediting, recognition and oversight bodies
- Effective, visual display of data facilitates analysis of trends and opportunities for improvement.

Discussions

- New ability for inter-facility discussion/communication/ and benchmarking
- Review of results promoted sharing best practices
- Enhanced reporting provided more accurate comparisons
- Brainstormed for initiatives that foster standardized procedures
- Renewed efforts to improve data quality
- Data table provided result comparison for eight consecutive quarters & trends clearly showed through graphs
- Dashboard fostered engagement in quality management and improvement activities
- Promoted systemwide improvement opportunities
- Reestablishment of the CALNOC data review committee

Implications for Practice

- Dashboard allows for review of data, identification of trends, and implementation of evidence-based quality improvements
- NSI Dashboard encourages conversations among nursing leaders
- Reflects three aspects of nursing care: structure, process, and outcomes.
- Brainstorming of dashboard format fosters standardized interventions
- Use of NSIs allows for measuring nursing compliance with policies and procedures

Limitations

- Limited generalization due to the sample size of end-users for this instrument
- Manual inputting of data into the CALNOC repository was highly labor-intensive.
- Lack of or limited human and other resources necessary for timely data submission into data repository.

For More Information

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References available upon request